

RE-DWELL Summer School 2 (Valencia)

Deliverable 3.5

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 3.5 RE-DWELL Summer School 2 (Valencia)

Version 1

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Table of contents

Executive summary.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
1.1. Contribution of local partners.....	7
1.2. Participants	7
1.3. RTM and TS training activities	9
1.4. Dissemination	1
2. Programme.....	3
2.1. Activities.....	5
2.2. Evaluation	20
3. Conclusion.....	27

Executive summary

This is a report on the second RE-DWELL Summer School, held at the Universitat Politècnica de València, which follows the successful first edition that took place at the University of Cyprus, Nicosia, from 15 to 20 November 2021. The third Summer school will be held at the University of Reading, in July 2023.

The programme of activities of the Valencia summer school aimed at fostering the exchange of knowledge across early-stage researchers (ESRs), supervisors and non-academic organisations, on the challenges and opportunities in Inclusive co-design and community planning of affordable and sustainable housing. The theme of the summer school, “Inclusive co-design and community planning of affordable and sustainable housing”, was thus addressed from multiple perspectives including invited speakers from professional practice and academia, local administrations and a local partner organisation. The presentations were followed by insightful group discussions and complemented by site visits to the eco-neighbourhood La Pinada , and to two examples of residential housing built by cooperatives: Santa María Micaela, from the 1960s, and Espai Verd, completed in the early 1990s. The series of open roundtables that started with the Lisbon workshop in September 2021, has continued with a fourth roundtable dedicated to address the question “How can community participation in the provision of affordable and sustainable housing be guided?”.

The programme of activities included meetings of ESRs and supervisors to follow-up on the development of ESR’s research as well as training activities related to two ongoing structured courses: “Comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis” (RMT2) and “Entrepreneurship - professional and career development” (TS2).

11 on-site and 4 on-line ESRs participated in the activities, along with XX supervisors/co-supervisors (8 on-site, 2 on-line), and one local partner organisation (in-person).

An exhibition of the on-going RE-DWELL work was on display on the School of Architecture in Valencia during the summer school.

Participants evaluated the course through an online survey, the results of which are presented in Section 2.2.

The work carried out in the Valencia summer school fostered an understanding of the significance of the inclusive co-design and community planning of affordable and sustainable housing in Europe. The summer school activities addressed the multiplicity of factors involved in a multi-stakeholder research approach (non-academics, local municipalities, civil society) and can serve as a basis for further RE-DWELL work.

1. Introduction

This report summarizes the work done during the second RE-DWELL summer school held in Valencia, from July 11 to 15, 2022, organized by the Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV). It encompasses the activities done by early-stage researchers (ESRs) prior to the workshop, the sessions facilitated by the tutors of RTM2 and TS2 courses, the programme of activities (ESRs research project presentations, onsite and online lectures and site visits), the outputs of the workshop, and the evaluation of the programme by ESRs and supervisors/co-supervisors.

As in the previous summer school in Nicosia, the programme of the Valencia summer school aimed at fostering the exchange of knowledge across ESRs, supervisors and non-academic organisations, on the challenges and opportunities of the design process in realizing needs for affordable and sustainable housing. The programme of activities was thus designed to enable a follow-up on the development of ESR's research through training activities related to the ongoing structured courses (two sessions on "Research, Methods and Tools 2-RMT2" and "Transferrable Skills 2-TS2") and through networking activities between the individual projects, supervisors/co-supervisors and partner organisation.

The summer school addressed the theme of "Inclusive co-design and community planning of affordable and sustainable housing". The programme encompassed five sub-themes which are part of the RE-DWELL training structure:

- **Design of affordable and sustainable housing** – challenges and opportunities that inclusive co-design and community planning of affordable and sustainable housing offers to architects and planners, developers and inhabitants; understanding the building/community relationships and opportunities.
- **Transdisciplinarity research for affordable and sustainable housing** – theoretical grounding of the ESRs' research projects in a transdisciplinary manner; analysis and position of ESR's own research and relations with other peers' projects.
- **Participatory processes** – factors involved in housing participation and co-housing; experiences and methods.
- **Comparative research methods** – training on comparative housing research; alignment of research methods with individual research projects.
- **Transferrable skills** – training on entrepreneurship skills; professional and career development: roles and competences.

Invited speakers from professional practice, academia, the local partner organisation and the local municipalities addressed topics related to the summer school's theme. The lectures were followed by insightful group discussions and were complemented by site visits in Valencia. A roundtable to discuss "How can community participation in the provision of affordable and sustainable housing be guided", open to the public via an online session, was moderated by Nadia Charalambous, UCY.

Some preparatory work was carried out by the ESRs which included:

- for the “Comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis” (RMT2) course, a collaborative map of research methodologies, an individual essay on comparative methods and a peer-review of another essay.
- for the “Entrepreneurship - professional and career development” (TS2), to review RE-DWELL CDP and to explore the potential doctoral graduate careers that they envisage and why. This includes reviewing their individual CDPs in preparation for the workshop in Valencia.

Throughout the different activities of the programme, ESRs had the opportunity to demonstrate their ability to analyse and position their own research and that of another ESRs within the field of housing studies, to reflect on their own research work and on the work of their peers, to improve their understanding of comparative methodologies for qualitative and quantitative analysis in general and in relation to their own projects, to improve their understanding of the entrepreneurship and professional career and to engage with several external UPV stakeholders.

The structure and outcome of RE-DWELL’s summer schools can provide an insightful resource for academics and researchers within the field of housing studies, fostering an understanding of the compatibility between affordable and sustainable housing across Europe through a holistic and transdisciplinary research and training programme.

1.1. Contribution of local partners

The Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) was in charge of organising the summer school. A fruitful collaboration, established with local non-academic organisations, enriched the program of the summer school and strengthened the ties with different and diverse stakeholders involved in the housing sector. The local partner organisation, Sustainable Towns S.L, the municipalities of Valencia, Green Building Council, CARPE, monoDestudio Cooperative, EVha, Entitat Valenciana d’Habitatge i Sól, Crearqció Cooperative and Doméstiques research lab, Fent Estudi Cooperative, played a key role in accomplishing the learning objectives of the summer school. Sustainable Towns S.L, the local partner organization, was in charge of organizing one session of the programme with the site visit of La Pinada, a sustainable neighbourhood in process.

1.2. Participants

10 members of the RE-DWELL beneficiaries and partners organisations participated in-person in the summer school, and 2 were participating online (Table 1):

Table 1. Participants from beneficiaries and partner organisations

	Beneficiary / Partner organisation	Member	Presence
1.	B1 FUNITEC (La Salle-URL), Spain, Project Coordinator	Leandro Madrazo	On-line
2.	B1 FUNITEC (La Salle-URL), Spain, Project Coordinator	Nuria Martí	In-person
3.	B3 University of Sheffield, United Kingdom	Krzysztof Nawrotek	In-person
4.	B4 University of Zagreb, Croatia	Gojko Bezovan	In-person
5.	B5 Hungarian Academy of Sciences Centre of Excellence, Hungary	Adrienne Csizmady	In-person
6.	B6 University of Cyprus, Cyprus	Nadia Charalambous	In-person
7.	B7 Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain	Carla Sentieri	In-person
8.	B7 Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain	Ignacio Guillen	In-person
9.	B8 TU Delft, Netherlands	Gerard van Bortel	In-person
10.	B8 TU Delft, Netherlands	Marietta Haffner	On-line
11.	B9 ISCTE- Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Portugal	Alexandra Paio	In-person
12.	P02 Sustainable Towns, Spain	Iker Marcaide	In-person

11 ESRs were present, and 3 followed the sessions on-line (Table 2):

Table 2. Participants early-stage researchers

ESR #	ESR name	Presence
1.	Annette Davis	In-person
2.	Saskia Furman	In-person
3.	Christophe Verrier	In-person
4.	Aya Elghandour	On-line
5.	Mahmoud Alsaeed	In-person
6.	Marko Horvat	In-person
7.	Anna Martin	In-person
8.	Andreas Panagidis	In-person
9.	Effrosyni Roussou	In-person
10.	Zoe Tzika	In-person
11.	Tijn Croon	On-line
12.	Alex Fernández	Absent
13.	Androniki Pappa	In-person
14.	Carolina Martín	In-person
15.	Leonardo Ricaurte	On-line

1.3. RTM and TS training activities

A follow-up on the development of ESR's research was facilitated through training activities related to the ongoing structured courses : “Comparative methodologies for qualitative and quantitative analysis” (RMT2) (Figure 1) and “Entrepreneurship - professional and career development” (TS2) (Figure 2).

Research Methods and Tools 2 (RMT2)

Figure 1. RMT2 course structure as integrated with the network activities.
From: Gerard van Bortel (TUD)

Transferable Skills 2 (TS2)

Figure 2. TS2 course structure as integrated with the network activities.
From: Karim Hadjri (USFD), Transferable Skills 2 (TS2)

1.4. Dissemination

The programme of the summer school was disseminated in different media including UPV (Figure 3), the RE-DWELL social media channels (Figure 4) and the project [website](#). The roundtable was promoted in the RE-DWELL social media channels (Figures 5 and 6).

Figure 3. Dissemination in UPV Facebook

Figure 4. Dissemination of the summer school activities in RE-DWELL Twitter channel

Figure 5. Announcement of Roundtable #4 in RE-DWELL Instagram channel

Figure 6. Announcement of Roundtable #4 in RE-DWELL Twitter channel

An exhibition of the ongoing research of RE-DWELL consisting of 17 A0 panels, 2 to introduce the network and 15 dedicated to each ESRs work (abstract, diagram, vocabulary terms, case studies, blogposts). Together with the panels, there was a collection of recent press releases about the problems of affordable housing in Europe collected by ESRs along with works of the subject "Housing Renovation" of the Master of Architecture at the UPV (Figures 7 and 8).

Figures 7, 8. RE-DWELL exhibition at the School of Architecture. Valencia, July 2022

After the summer school, the exhibition was on display at CTAV, Col·legi Territorial d'Arquitectes de València, from 8 to 22 September, 2022 (Figures 9 and 10).

Figures 9. RE-DWELL exhibition at CTAV, Col·legi Territorial d'Arquitectes de València, September 2022

Figure 10. RE-DWELL exhibition at CTAV, Col·legi Territorial d'Arquitectes de València, September 2022

2. Programme

The summer school took place at the Architecture School at the Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain, from July 11 to 15, 2022. It was an on-site event, although its development was still conditioned by the COVID-19 pandemic which prevented the attendance of two supervisors. Thus, most of the sessions were delivered in a hybrid mode (in-person and online).

The programme was divided in daily sessions which interlinked training and research activities with presentations by external stakeholders from professional practice, academia and local municipalities, as well as site visits (Table 3).

Table 3. Programme of the Summer School

Day	Timetable	Activities
DAY 1 Monday, 11 July, 2022	09:00 to 9:30	Welcome
	9:30 to 11:30	Affordable and sustainable housing in Valencia
	11:45 to 13:00	Exhibition
	13:00 to 14:15	Lunch
	14:15 to 18:30	ESR projects workshop
	20:00	Dinner
DAY 2 Tuesday, 12 July, 2022	09:30 to 12:30	RMT2 Course
	13:00 to 14:15	Lunch
	14:15 to 15:30	In-person meetings ESRs and supervisors
	15:30 to 18:00	Participation and community processes
	20:00	Dinner
DAY 3 Wednesday, 13 July, 2022	09:30 to 12:30	Experiences of participation and community processes
	13:00 to 14:15	Lunch
	14:15 to 15:15	A new perspective for a sustainable neighbourhood
	15:15 to 18:00	Visit to Santa María Micaela
	20:00	Dinner
DAY 4 Thursday, 14 July, 2022	09:30 to 11:30	Roundtable
	11:30 to 12:30	Visit to Espai Verd
	13:00 to 14:15	Lunch
	14:15 to 16:15	In-person meetings ESRs and supervisors
	16:15 to 18:30	Vocabulary / Case study library
	20:00	Dinner
DAY 5 Friday, 15 July, 2022	09:30 to 12:30	TS2 course
	13:00 to 14:15	Lunch
	14:14 to 16:15	Session: Last reflections ES
	16.15 to 18:30	Walking tour social housing in Velluters
	20:00	Dinner

2.1. Activities

DAY 1

Monday, 11 March

Welcome

In the opening session, Leandro Madrazo, network coordinator, welcomed the participants (online) along with the dean of the School of Architecture, Ivan Cabrera, and the summer school coordinator Carla Sentieri (Figures 11 and 12).

Figures 11 and 12. Welcome session. Ivan Cabrera, Dean, School of Architecture, UPV

Affordable and sustainable housing in Valencia

This first session provided an overview of sustainable design, a historical evolution of Valencia and an ongoing research project aimed at reducing CO2 emissions in Valencia (Figures 13, 14 and 15).

- Bruno Sauer, Technical Director of the Green Building Council Spain. Sustainable design to create value over time.
- Adolfo Vigil, Assistant Professor, Department of Urbanism, UPV. Valencia: historical evolution and future challenges.
- Ignacio Guillen, Architect, Professor, School of Architecture, UPV. Missions Valencia 2030.

Figures 13-15. Presentations. Affordable and sustainable housing in Valencia

The ESRs who were following the summer school activities on line acted as rapporteurs. This was the summary of the session facilitated by Leonardo Ricaurte:

“On the one hand, from Sauer’s presentation the questions posed to the audience about who defines the value of sustainable design, who puts the price and the role of architects in this process in the context of the wider population; are quite aligned with some of the current debates about social value in the UK, especially when applied to the built environment. These questions could be further developed if, for instance, we problematise the need to have to subject any design intervention and outcome to a financial proxy. When it comes to quantifying the impact on people’s well-being of ‘good’ architecture it is impossible to avoid the subjective nature of the enquiry. These are some of the issues that my research project is attempting to address. Utilising POE as an opportunity to incorporate the inhabitants’ feedback on the question of valuing housing design.

On the other hand, Guillen’s presentation revolved around the current smart city strategy that the municipality of Valencia is trying to implement. A very ambitious and remarkable endeavour to put the city at the forefront of innovation and real-time mapping to support and inform decision-making. It is relevant to underscore the contribution of international frameworks and good practices that this project incorporates. The application of the New Urban Agenda or the SDGs to more tangible actions has a great potential to demonstrate their applicability and inspire other municipalities to get on board with these types of initiatives.”

ESR projects workshop

Group activity replicating the scenario-based methodology of the [Workshop](#) at the Helsinki International Social Housing Festival, in June 2022. ESR Zoe Tzika organised the session (Figures 16, 17)

The aim of this workshop was to provide a space for the ESRs to present, discuss and compare their on-going research projects. ESRs had the opportunity to share their work and exchange feedback and ideas in an interactive way. They presented their research project to each other, asking questions, discussing, and giving feedback. The supervisors were also engaged in the discussion. Notes of the discussion were kept on a shared Miro board, relating, and connecting the research projects (Figure 18).

Figures 16, 17. ESRs Project workshop

DAY 2

Tuesday, 12 July

RMT2 Course: Comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis

Facilitator: Gerard van Bortel, TUD

RTM2 training activities on the sub-theme of “Comparative methodologies for qualitative and quantitative analysis” were organized in the morning session.

Each ESR was assigned a peer-reviewer for their essay on research methods. Then, the peer reviews were discussed in small groups (Figures 19, 20). At the end of the session there was a plenary discussion of the emerging topics. Finally, the ESRs were invited to revise their essays based on the feedback received and complete them before end of October.

The following is a list of comparative housing research issues addressed in the essays:

- Comparing case study results from Academia (Solar Decathlon), Industry, and local government
- Comparing energy poverty measurement techniques
- Comparative analysis of housing systems based on a small number of cases
- Comparing and triangulating methodologies and methods in exploratory inquiries
- Comparative analyses of case studies (using qualitative and quantitative methods)
- Need for a more localized scale of comparison
- Generalisability of variables found in a single case study
- Creating a transferable concept of housing precariat and related body of knowledge
- Transferability of guidelines for sustainable local development through urban commons across different contexts

Figures 19, 20. RMT2 Course: Comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis

In-person meetings ESRs and supervisors

During the first part of the afternoon, ESRs met with supervisors and co-supervisors to discuss the progress of their research project.

Participation and community processes.

The session included three presentations from invited speakers from professional practice. Blanca Pedrola, Irene from Carpe y Jordi Quiñonero from monoEstudio. They showed examples of participatory processes in urban contexts in which they had participated.

- Blanca Pedrola, architect, Associate Professor, CEU Cardenal Herrera University. Green and inclusive cities for and with people.
- Irene Reig, architect and civic designer, member of CARPE. The collective construction of the city.
- Jordi Quiñonero, expert in planning of participatory processes, monoDestudio Cooperative. People's engagement in dwelling projects.

The presentations were followed by questions and answers with the ESRs (Figures 21, 22 and 23).

Figure 21-23. Blanca Pedrola, Irene Reig and Jordi Quiñonero

The three presentations revolved around experiences with participatory processes in Spain with a series of case studies and were shown to highlight opportunities, threats and crucial considerations that prevent or enable the success of these initiatives.

ESR Tijn Croon was the rapporteur for this session:

“Ms. Pedrola discussed the importance of green spaces in the urban fabric, but also emphasised that these spaces must foster social interaction. Particularly with the urban inequalities that we see, not only in terms of divergent economic opportunities but also in terms of the ever greater differences in health conditions, building for people is extremely important.

Ms. Reig’s talk connected well with the one of Dr. Pedrola, who also discussed the importance of a sense of ownership and belonging. She emphasised that social activities can foster these perceptions.

Mr. Quiñonero discussed modern participatory processes. -For me as a public policy researcher, I found it interesting that he distinguished three ‘levels of governance’ in the involvement of stakeholders: consultive, cooperative, and integrated. Obviously, this went from marginal to greater involvement. It made me think of the literature I read on recognitional justice, and ‘fair’ and ‘transparent’ decision-making.”

DAY 3

Wednesday, 13 July

Experiences of participation and community processes

The session included three presentations from invited speakers from professional practice, and members of the local municipality of Valencia.

- María Flores, César Mifsut, EVha , Entitat Valenciana d'Habitatge i Sòl. Social housing strategies and citizen participation.
- Júlia Gomar, Julia Pineda, Crearçió Cooperative and Domèstiques research lab. Researching and managing housing cooperatives.
- Isabel González, Fran Azorín, Fent Estudi Cooperative. Collaborative design of living scenarios.

Maria Flores and César Mifsut presented housing cases and strategies that are being carried out with citizen participation in the provision of social housing from municipal management in the Community of Valencia. Julia Gomar and Julia Pineda spoke about the experience of housing cooperatives in local contexts. Following the processes of Sostre Cívic, they advise communities to form cooperatives and initiate participatory processes. Isabel González presented cases of collaborative processes both at the university and in neighbourhoods in Valencia (Figures 24, 25).

Figures 24, 25. Maria Flores y Cesar Misfut; Isabel González

The presentations were followed by questions and answers and a fruitful discussion with the ESRs (Figures 26, 27).

Figures 26, 27. Discussion with the ESRs

A new perspective for a sustainable neighbourhood

The programme included a presentation by Iker Marcaide, founder and business leader of the sustainable neighbourhood La Pinada, where a presentation followed by a discussion took place (Figures 28, 29). In the words of Iker Marcaide: "The La Pinada neighbourhood is the first eco-neighbourhood in Spain designed by its future inhabitants and conceived around a school. It is located in Paterna, in an area of 32 hectares, regenerating degraded land and creating a sustainable, healthy and resilient integral solution."

Participants visited the Imagine Montessori School of the neighbourhood (Figures 30-33), a building completed in 2019 which "makes a massive use of the materials with a lower ecological footprint: fired clay and wood. Clay is used for the bearing walls of perforated brick, for the vaults of solid brick, and on floors; and wood is used to build the structure and the roof panel, enclosures, and frames. There are neither claddings nor raised ceilings and floors. The brick wall is structure, partition, and cladding. Everything is exposed, showing how it works, how it is held, how it was built".¹

Figures 28, 29. Iker Marcaide's presentation

¹ <https://arquitecturaviva.com/works/colegio-imagine-montessori-paterna>

Figures 30-33. Visit to the school, La Pinada

Visit to Santa María Micaela

The experiences of participation and community processes presented in the morning session were complemented by a visit to a housing cooperative built in Valencia in the 1960s. The Santa María Micaela housing group, designed by Santiago Artal Ríos in 1958, was built between 1959 and 1961 for the Cooperativa de Agentes Comerciales in a block in the Segundo Ensanche of Valencia, located near the old Turia riverbed. At the time, it represented an important urbanistic alteration of the municipal planning, which contemplated a typical closed block solution. It consists of three linear blocks: two twelve-storey blocks, parallel to each other, with commercial ground floors, perpendicular to a smaller block (3 floors). The in-between spaces are organized around a water pond which acts as a bioclimatic element (Figures 34, 35). The aim was to obtain the best possible sunlight and ventilation for the dwellings and to integrate the interior urban space with the residential units (Figure 36).

Figures 34, 35. Santa Maria Micaela: exterior spaces

Figure 36. Santa Maria Micaela: inside a housing unit

DAY 4

Thursday, 14 July

Round table “How can community participation in the provision of affordable and sustainable housing be guided?”

An open discussion on how community participation in the provision of affordable and sustainable housing can be guided focusing on processes, obstacles and best practices for community participation in contemporary housing design.

The round table was moderated by Nadia Charalambous, UCY. Guest speakers were:

- Anne Kockelkorn, Associate Professor of Architecture, Co-director of the Master of Advanced Studies in History and Theory of Architecture, ETH Zurich.
- Blanca Pedrola, architect, Associate Professor, CEU Cardenal Herrera University.
- Isabel González, architect, Fent Estudi Cooperative.

The speakers discussed the challenges and opportunities that affordable and sustainable housing planning and design poses for architects and planners, developers and inhabitants, forms of collaborative housing, co-production, social innovation, and social experimentation in housing and neighbourhoods and the building/community relationships and opportunities.

ESR Leonardo Ricaurte acted as rapporteur of the discussion, these were the major points:

“The relevance of the approach to the context. This should be a gradual, incremental and careful process. As highlighted in Wednesday’s session on the methodology developed by Fent Estudi, there are different layers of reality to be considered: consensus, invisible and essential. Also, the various intersectional considerations of facilitators and participants alike should be given enough attention.

There is no magical tool or one-size-fits-all methodology that can be applied to all cases. Keeping a reflexive and open attitude is crucial, each context will demand certain things that might be unique. All communities are different even within the same city, social background or neighbourhood. Different processes require different tools.

When asked about relevant methods or activities, one of the speakers referred to the ‘exploratory walks’ as an engaging and productive method to lead participants to a better understanding of the place and spatial considerations.

How do we engage with diversity? This is another significant question that we should all ask ourselves and our team when conducting such processes. Different social, ethnic, gender, and cultural differences must be engaged effectively. To count with a thorough description and mapping of the community’s composition is a very handy piece of information.

The policy instruments and political and institutional support are quite remarkable features of the Swiss case. The cost rent and the non-profit notion of the collective benefit have been instrumental in the advance of cooperatives in cities like Zurich. A very strong and engaged civil movement, where architects’ participation has been very relevant, is another driving force behind the success of housing cooperatives.

Likewise, according to Anne Kockelkorn, the market is quite ‘fragmented’ and open where there are numerous smaller organisations that can participate underpinned by the regulatory and

financial possibilities available, contrary to a monopoly or oligopoly. The trust that exists in all parties is another characteristic that facilitates low-interest bank loans making it possible to run a cooperative with a comparatively low budget in the inception phase. The Swiss banking system is stable and trustworthy and this has a prominent role in the fertile environment for housing cooperatives to grow.

Another tip given by the speakers is the importance of tracking down the existing spaces of participation. Places, where people often meet can be used as the starting point for a participatory process. Instead of imposing something, we should rather adapt to what people are used to.

The translation of desires into a spatial design can be bridged by a wise creation of the brief. Architecture competitions can be successful in translating people's ideas but this will be only the case if the brief is co-created and shared in an open and deliberative process. Guidance from architects is crucial to creating a brief that is realistic and tangible enough to become a spatial reality.

The importance of envisaging an adequate co-management and takeover strategy was reiterated. The long-term management of schemes is something that should be thoroughly considered before the exit strategy.

Another interesting remark was that not everyone might be interested or willing to engage in participatory processes. Innovative housing schemes are not everyone's cup of tea, cohousing and collaborative housing are time-consuming and require a certain type of inhabitant that enjoys having an active social life. This poses a challenge in current times where participation has become increasingly important. There should be different models of engagement that recognise this reality.

In a design note, a recent observation was shared with the panel. The fragmentation of common spaces has been seen as more effective than having a central and spatially important space. The smaller spaces promote faster and easier appropriation by the residents and also contribute to the spatial and functional variety of the scheme. The space is continuously created and reinterpreted by its users.“

The presentations were followed by a fruitful discussion with ESRs and the project coordinator (Figures 37, 38).

The [video](#) of the roundtable is available in the RE-DWELL website (Figure 39).

Figures 37, 38. Round Table and discussion

Figure 39. Publication of the roundtable in RE-DWELL website

Visit to Espai Verd

At the beginning of the 1980s, the architectural firm CSPT (Antonio Cortés, Alfonso Serrano, Salvador Pérez and Toni Carrascosa) specialised in the design, building and management of residential buildings with cooperatives. These non-profit projects allowed them to experiment and search for the best possible habitats for the users. Thus, most of the projects carried out by CSPT provided open spaces and green areas to foster interpersonal relations, with . Espai Verd was an initiative of a housing cooperative, and the first phase was completed in 1991. Far removed from the most conservative academic visions, Espai Verd supports a model of collective housing design and construction in which decisions are shared among the future inhabitants in close collaboration with architect Antonio Cortés, who is also living here, guided us through the building (Figures 40-41).

Figures 40-41. Visit to Espai Verd

In-person meetings ESRs with supervisors

During the first part of the afternoon, ESRs met with supervisors and co-supervisors to discuss the progress of their research projects (Figures 42, 43).

Figures 42, 43. Meetings of ESRs with supervisors

Vocabulary / Case study library

The session led by Leandro Madrazo was dedicated to reviewing the on-going collaborative research work which is being done through the RE-DWELL vocabulary and case study library. The session was carried out in a blended format, in-person and on-line. An online presentation about the current status of the work done was followed by a team activity in which ESRs answered to a series of questions which were then shared and discussed with the whole group (Figure 44).

The vocabulary and case study library are two instruments to create a knowledge base about affordable and sustainable housing in collaboration. They are also key for the transdisciplinary research approach that RE-DWELL's is adopting. Together, they fulfil a double purpose:

- for researchers, they are an instrument to foster communication and collaboration across individual ESR project.
- for external audiences, they are a contribution to the field of affordable and sustainable housing, mostly for academics and researchers, potentially for other stakeholders.

Vocabulary

The construction of the shared vocabulary has different purposes:

- At the individual level: Developing basic instrumental skills: exercising writing (discourse, narrative, vocabulary), referencing, expressing oneself with clarity; and addressing wide audiences in an understandable language.
- At the collective level: Getting to know key concepts from other disciplinary perspective; establishing links with your our conceptual framework; and identifying shared topics to be developed outside the vocabulary, in other contexts (papers, reports,...)
- At the knowledge construction level: Building a framework to address affordable and sustainable housing from a transdisciplinary perspective.

After the presentation, ESRs were divided in teams to prepare answers for the following questions:

- Considering the vocabulary entries you have written so far: what was useful for you? What did you learn?
- What was useful for the collective research of the network? Which links/shared activities were facilitated by the vocabulary construction?
- What could be done to make the vocabulary more useful, at the individual and collective level?
- What could be done to make the vocabulary useful for external audiences? Which sort of audience?

Figure 44. Vocabulary/case study session

Case study library

Some critical issues concerning the content and objectives of the in-progress library were addressed in the presentation:

- There is a risk of providing similar contents that we can find in other sources (e.g. Wikipedia, blogs, publications).
- Which insights does your documentation of the cases provide on affordable and sustainable housing?
- Is there a balance between information provided by other sources and the added value of your judgement?.

After the presentation, ESRs were asked to provide answers to the following questions:

- Taking into account the case studies you have analysed so far: How have they been useful to you? What have you learned?
- Could you identify the importance of the case for the intertwined research areas considered in RE-DWELL?
- Could you identify the relevance of the cases with regard to the SDGs?
- What could be done to make the case study library more useful for researchers?
- What could be done to make the contents useful for external audiences? Which ones?

DAY 5

Friday, 15 July

TS2 Course: Entrepreneurship - professional and career development

Facilitator: Krzysztof Nawratek (USFD)

TS2 session consisted of a mini-lecture followed by a workshop, with the aims fomenting skills in career development planning, and to enhance ESRs' awareness of career opportunities and paths (Figures 45, 46). The mini-lecture discussed the implementation of a career plan using the RE-DWELL CDP as an example. It also introduced ESRs to the value of a CDP, its management and implementation.

The seminar led to group activities using the RDF Cards to answer specific questions related to career pathways. The following questions were discussed using the RDF cards:

- How do you develop a career plan?
- What are your career options post-PhD?
- Which career pathway are you interested in?

The programme for the session was as follows:

- 10:00: Welcome and introduction to the session
- 10:05: Lecture: Implementing a career plan and RE-DWELL CDP
- 10:30: Workshop: CDP overview - doctoral graduate careers. RDF Development Cards
- 12:45: Concluding remarks.
- 13:00: End

Figures 45, 46. Transferable Skills session (TS2)

2.2. Evaluation

The workshop was evaluated by all the participants online, through an anonymous online questionnaire (see Annex 1). The main goal of the questionnaire was to evaluate their experience and to detect any elements that could be improved in the last workshop and summer school.

The online questionnaire was answered by 10 ESRs, 4 supervisors/co-supervisors.

In the first part of the survey participants were asked to assign a rating a general view. In the second part, they had to identify what they particularly liked and what could have been done better. At the end of the survey, they could add comments and recommendations for upcoming network activities (see Annex 1 - Event evaluation form) .

All the sessions were generally well considered. The majority of the participants evaluated the overall organization of the summer school. positively (see Table 4).

Table 4. Summary of the evaluation

Questions	Answers	Supervisors/Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
How would you rate the organization of the summer school? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	5	4,80	4,86
Please evaluate "Affordable and sustainable housing in Valencia" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	13	4,50	4,67	4,62
Please evaluate "Exhibition" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	13	5	4,89	4,92
Please evaluate "ESR projects workshop" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4,75	4,80	4,79
Please evaluate "Research Methodologies and Tools 2" course (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	12	5	4,30	4,42
Please evaluate "In-person meetings ESRs and supervisors" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4,25	4	4,07
Please evaluate "Participation and community processes" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4,50	4,70	4,64
Please evaluate "Experiences of participation and community processes" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	5,00	4,50	4,64
Please evaluate "A new perspective for a sustainable neighbourhood" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4,50	4,50	4,50

Please evaluate "Visit to Santa María Micaela" (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4,75	4,20	4,36
Please evaluate "Roundtable" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4,25	4,50	4,43
Please evaluate "Visit to Espai Verd" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4,50	4,30	4,36
Please evaluate "In-person meetings ESRs with supervisors" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	13	4,25	4	4,08
Please evaluate "Vocabulary / Case study library" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	12	4,67	4,33	4,42
Please evaluate "Transferrable Skills 2" course (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	12	5	4,44	4,58
Please evaluate "Meeting ESRs and supervisors" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	9	5	3,75	3,89
Please evaluate "Walking tour social housing in Velluters" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	8	4,50	4,17	4,25

An analysis of the answers to each of the questions linked to each activity can give an overall picture of the outcome of the summer school.

The majority of the ESRs answered positively to the "Affordable and sustainable housing in Valencia" session:

"Very interesting introduction and useful in order to understand the context that we are in."

"Interesting session with a variety of professionals with different viewpoints."

"Well experienced speakers provided interesting insights"

"Very interesting presentations, great input for those of us that relate to community participation"

"Excellent speakers. I found Bruno's presentation very useful for my project and had a discussion with him afterwards. As Prof. Ignacio's work was very important for our project "Indicators for a Sustainable City", it would be great to invite him again"

"I think it was a very interesting session, introducing us to the context of the affordable and sustainable projects in Valencia"

However, one supervisor mentioned that:

"The presentation about Valencia should have focussed more on social housing."

Regarding the “Exhibition”, all the comments were very positive. These were some of the comments:

“Great idea, having a space for exhibiting our current projects.”

“Very interesting way of presenting our work, and I believe all of us cannot possibly thank Carla enough for this. It has also contributed to making the summer school much less stressful than that of Valencia, given that what was required of us in order for this exhibition to take place, could be easily and quickly fulfilled”.

“I think is a good way to have a global vision of the project”.

“The exhibition was impressively presented. I really appreciated all the work done by the workshop organiser (Carla). It was great that she managed to prepare such a good exhibition without so much input from our side, because we were really busy finalising a lot of tasks before the summer”.

Regarding the “ESR projects workshop” sessions, the rating was mostly positive. The open discussions between the ERS were very productive. Some relevant comments:

“We definitely need more informal discussions and avoid as much as possible formal presentations with a more or less passive audience.”.

“The best part to understand each other’s topics and where they are in their research”.

“Though different to the programme it was a great time slot to speak about each of our projects in turn to be updated on the current direction and state of research and be able to make connections to our own projects”.

“This session was a very nice experience for us ESRs. Now that our projects are getting together, we have so much to exchange and we gain huge knowledge from unstructured discussions without stress. The fact that we didn’t want to finish the session is representative of its success”.

“It was the first time we had engaged in an open and clear discussion. I think it would be great to do it again”.

“The personal conversation with the students was very informative and revealing. We were able to work much more efficiently than with online meetings. It would have been nice if more of the supervisors could attend in person”.

“This session gave us an opportunity to discuss almost informally about how our projects are going”.

Regarding the “RMT2 Course: Comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis” session, the rating was mostly positive but there were different opinions. Relevant comments:

“Very useful! Peer-reviews among us is a great way to have feedback!”.

“In order for a successful and meaningful peer review to take place, we need to either be actual peers, as in share the same educational background, or build a foundation, a common ground on which to facilitate communication and understanding between the different disciplines involved in this project. Unfortunately the vocabulary project is not really helpful when we barely know what our peers' fields are about”.

“In general well organised but could be improved by adding some examples of other persons research and how they used research methods. Peer review content is not always about methods... can at times drift toward theory instead of methodologies.”

Regarding “In-person meeting ESRs and supervisors” sessions (on Tuesday and Thursday), they were positively rated by all ESRs.

“Not really much time left for my supervisors and me to meet, but overall a good opportunity to update everyone on the current state of my research”.

“I didn't have one. I prefer this time in next activities to be replaced by a session delivered by any of our supervisors for example to explain as a certain skill they think it is useful for ESRs to learn about. Or how they manage/organize their time to write papers, teach, or write a book. For example I imagine Flora Samuel can give us a session on what does ideology of research means this philosophical side of research is confusing for many of us. If a supervisor explains it in simple terms and what are the different types of ideologies to choose from”.

“Much needed session to be able to meet together in person as the discussions are always more fruitful compared to online meetings”.

“Very useful initiative. However it is not always easy to coordinate these meetings resulting in some people not getting to have their meetings at all. In any case, we have the chance to discuss our research with our supervisors in more informal settings during the summer school (from breakfast, dinner, bus etc)”.

“The concept is excellent. However, it was quite difficult to get answers from industry partners and supervisors as we received the programme a week before summer school”.

Regarding “Participation and community processes” session, it was positively rated by all ESRs. These comments exemplify the general view. There are some complains about one presentation online. It shows that is better to have the conferences on-site.

“Very interesting presentations as well. Many of us found useful connections for our research and case studies”.

“Like the first day, the presentations were excellent and useful”.

“It was great to see so many participatory processes going on in the city”.

“Great selection of presentations and excellent final discussion”.

Regarding “Experiences of participation and community processes” session, it was positively rated by all ESRs too.

“We had a global vision from different points of view: institutional, urban processes and housing processes”.

“Although the topics were a bit far from my research, I had a few questions that were answered by the panel and were very useful for my project”.

“We had the chance to listen to very interesting lecturers and to establish an good discussion”.

Regarding “A new perspective for a sustainable neighbourhood” session organize by the partner organization, was positively rated by all ESRs too.

“The visit to the school was good and it helped for understanding the objective of the neighbourhood”.

“Excellent to see how entrepreneurship can make a good change. We could invite Iker again to give more details”.

Regarding “Visit to Santa María Micaela” the comments were diverse. Some were positive.

“Great experience to visit inside the home with the residents and better understand the experience of living in a cooperative”.

“The two architects that showed us around did an amazing explanation of the building and had the kindness of showing us their own home. It was a pleasure to visit this extraordinary building”.

Others weren't so positive

“Not really social housing, but interesting to see prior examples of housing estates”

“Not as relevant as other events”.

Regarding the “Roundtable” session, it was positively rated by all ESRs. These comments exemplify the general view:

“Great discussion but very focussed on cooperative housing and participation which isn't the main topic of all of our projects”.

“Great round of exchanges. Nadia's facilitation was a blessing. She covered all the key points in her questions in a way that it was hard for us to think of more insightful questions”.

“As always, the round table was very engaging, although I wish we had had more time to ask more questions”.

Regarding the “Visit to Espai Verd” session, it was positively rated by some ESRs and for others wasn't so relevant. These comments exemplify the general view:

“By far the most interesting site visit we had so far, the building was a gem”.

“A privilege to visit and meet the architect and see an example of urban housing which has managed to incorporate nature/plants in such a way - very inspiring”.

“Amazing experience and a great tour. I am very thankful that I had the chance meet the actual architect of the complex and listen to his narrative. Almost like a live documentary”.

“Not so relevant from a research perspective, but again great opportunity to visit some local examples of housing”.

Regarding the “Vocabulary/case study library” session, it was positively rated the ESRs. These comments exemplify the general view:

“Time to reflect upon the use of both, and an opportunity to think about how we can improve the collaboration among us. I think the idea that was raised at the last meeting was great, co-writing an entry during our on-site meetings”

“It was good to express our opinions and thoughts. Enjoyed the discussions with my colleagues”.

“It is nice that the discussion was made in the form of a workshop. We feel that it is a collaborative work and the session was very well organised”.

Regarding “TS2 Course: Entrepreneurship; professional and career development” session, it was positively rated the ESRs. These comments exemplify the general view:

“Interesting, albeit generic workshop on the skills and values necessary to venture beyond academia”.

“This session was the one freaking me out the most. I felt like it is going to be “you need to dream and change the world and do things no one did before” and this kind of talk. However Nawartek was very realistic and honest give us practical advice on how to be open to different opportunities. It is good to have a plan but it is good also to be flexible. I had a huge sense of comfort after this session. The activity organized was very important to interact and understand what HRs are looking for. The charts were very useful and definitely I will get back to it when I do my CDP. Giving us an example of himself doing a CDP was really useful. Like we saw how Professors do it. How they manifest and put ideas on papers without worrying too much how it is going to be finalized now”.

Regarding “Meeting ESRs and supervisors” session, it was positively rated the ESRs. This comment exemplify the general view:

“Despite the misunderstanding with the time schedule, I think that this meeting was fruitful and constructive. I do believe that having this continuous communication about the progress of the project is fundamental for improvement and I'm glad that there was time reserved for this”.

Regarding other comments or suggestions for upcoming onsite RE-DWELL network activities, some ESRs suggested the following:

“Valencia Summer School was a unique experience for us that participated. We realise that we are becoming a group with the other ESRs and our supervisors. The structure and the implementation of the program combined rich input by external presenters, knowledge exchange and a lot of fun. It was very efficient that we didn't have to prepare stressful deliverables but instead we discussed about our work as it is now, or some aspects of it that concern us, or anything from the bigger view to a small detail that we wished to share. In my opinion at the point that we are now as a group, this activity should be an example for the future events. Thank you for organising and everyone that participated”.

“I think the fact that we didn't have so much workload during this Summer School, made the whole experience much more enjoyable. Without having the pressure of doing presentations, without having to grade/compete between our panels, and other deadlines, created a much more relaxed and participatory atmosphere. People asked many questions during the lectures and continued the interesting discussions after they ended. We gave feedback to our individual projects in an informal way that otherwise in a formal presentation with a limited time would have never happened. I think this summer school helped to create group cohesion more than others.

“Maybe for other workshops it would be good to be more flexible in what each of the ESR's has to present. Instead of asking the same output from all of them, it would be better to ask them to show whatever they are developing at that stage, or they feel comfortable sharing. Additionally, I think it was great in this workshop that Carla made such a great effort to create those panels, minimising the workload for us and reducing the competitive feeling between panels”.

“It would be nice to have more time to discuss what you've heard. To process everything we heard on the spot”.

“At previous events, the documentary and the game received very good feedback. It would be good to integrate these into other events”.

Very good to include an introductory session on the local situation/issues at the beginning of the workshop.

Also, the presentation of real-life cases and the experience/reflection on lessons learned/challenges has been very well organised and very useful.

3. Conclusion

The summer school helped to foster the knowledge exchange between ESRs, supervisors, and non-academic organizations on the challenges and opportunities of “Inclusive co-design and community planning of affordable and sustainable housing.” In particular, it contributed to enhancing the knowledge of the participants about housing cooperatives, the advantages and disadvantages of users’ participation, the difficulties to implement participatory processes and the need to adapt them to the local conditions in each case. We are beginning to see how the research work carried out by the ESRs is consolidating and collaborations are going to be established between some of the research projects. The vocabulary is helping to create links between research projects and the case study library should facilitate further links. In summary, the activities carried out at the summer school contributed to a further step in building a collaborative and transdisciplinary research environment on the topic of affordable and sustainable housing.